

STRATEGIC PLAN FOR VEGETABLE CHIP PRODUCERS IN PLANZA, SAN FERNANDO, CAMARINES SUR

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the marketability of vegetable chips produced by selected crop producers in Planza, San Fernando, Camarines Sur, with the objective of developing a strategic plan to enhance competitiveness. Amid rising demand for healthy, value-added snacks, small-scale farmer-processors face structural and marketing constraints that limit market penetration. Guided by the Marketing Mix (7Ps), Value Chain Analysis, and Consumer Behavior Theory, the study employed a case study design using semi-structured interviews. Descriptive and strategic analyses, including SWOT and TOWS matrices, assessed internal capabilities and external conditions. Findings indicated that processors benefit from readily available raw materials and alignment with health-conscious consumption trends; however, limited marketing capabilities, weak brand identity, inadequate facilities, regulatory noncompliance, and strong competition from established brands constrain pricing flexibility and differentiation. The study concluded that although current marketability remains modest, significant growth potential exists through strategic intervention. A phased strategic plan emphasizing branding, digital marketing adoption, production efficiency, regulatory compliance, and entrepreneurship capacity-building was proposed. The study contributes a localized, resource-sensitive framework linking small-scale agricultural processing with sustainable market participation and regional economic development.

Keywords: *Marketability, Vegetable Chips, Value-Added Agriculture, Strategic Planning, Small-Scale Enterprises*

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains a critical driver of food security, rural livelihoods, and economic development, particularly in developing economies. In recent decades, the sector has undergone a structural transformation characterized by diversification from staple crops toward high-value crops (HVCs) and value-added agricultural products. This shift has been driven by changing consumer preferences, globalization of food markets, and the need to increase farm incomes through product differentiation and agro-processing. High-Value Crops, including coffee, cacao, fruits, vegetables, root crops, spices, and ornamentals, offer higher net returns compared to traditional staples and create opportunities for downstream processing and agribusiness expansion.

Among emerging value-added products, vegetable chips have gained increasing attention in both domestic and international markets due to rising health consciousness and demand for convenient, plant-based snack alternatives. The global healthy fruit and vegetable chips market was valued at approximately USD 11.4 billion in 2021 and is projected to reach USD 22.8 billion by 2030, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 8.1% (Grand View Research, 2024). This growth reflects broader consumption trends favoring minimally processed, nutrient-rich snack options. The expansion of this segment presents significant opportunities for small-scale agricultural producers to participate in higher-value supply chains through local processing and product innovation.

In the Philippine context, agriculture, forestry, and fishing contribute approximately 8.6–9.4% to the national Gross Domestic Product and provide livelihoods to about 23.2% of the population (Statista, 2024). Recognizing the need to enhance rural incomes and agribusiness competitiveness, the government has promoted diversification toward high-value crops through policy initiatives such as the High-Value Crops Development Program (HVCDP) under Republic Act No. 7900. The program aims to accelerate agricultural growth, improve farm productivity, and strengthen market linkages by encouraging the production and commercialization of high-value crops and processed products. Within this policy environment, vegetable chip production has emerged as a viable income-generating activity for farmer groups seeking to move beyond primary production into value addition.

Despite favorable market trends and policy support, small-scale farmer-processors often encounter structural and market-related constraints that limit their competitiveness. These challenges include limited market access, inadequate processing facilities, constrained marketing capabilities, and strong competition from established commercial snack brands. While existing literature has examined high-value crop promotion and agro-processing development at macro and industry levels, limited empirical research has focused on the marketability and strategic positioning of localized, farmer-led vegetable chip enterprises in rural Philippine settings. In particular, there remains insufficient analysis of how internal capabilities and external market conditions interact to shape the competitiveness of such enterprises.

Addressing this gap is important for both theory and practice. Understanding the market position and strategic situation of small-scale vegetable chip producers can inform targeted interventions, guide rural enterprise development, and contribute to evidence-based policy implementation under high-value crop programs.

Thus, this study aimed to assess the marketability of vegetable chips produced by selected crop producers in Planza, San Fernando, Camarines Sur, by analyzing their market position and competitive landscape. Specifically, it sought to examine internal strengths and weaknesses and external opportunities and threats to develop strategic recommendations that can enhance competitiveness and sustainability.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the strategic situation and marketability of vegetable chip producers in Planza, San Fernando, Camarines Sur, and to develop strategic recommendations to enhance their competitiveness.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the strategic situation of the selected vegetable chip producers in terms of their market position and competitive landscape?
 - 1.1 What are the internal strengths and weaknesses of the selected vegetable chip producers?
 - 1.2 What external opportunities and threats influence their operations?
 - 1.3 How do these internal and external factors affect their current market position?
2. What challenges do the selected vegetable chip producers encounter in operating and marketing their products?
 - 2.1 What financial constraints affect their production and expansion capacity?
 - 2.2 What marketing-related challenges limit their market reach and brand positioning?
 - 2.3 What infrastructure and processing limitations affect product quality and efficiency?
 - 2.4 What gaps exist in training and development among producers?
 - 2.5 What regulatory requirements pose operational challenges?
3. What strategic plan can be proposed to enhance the marketability and competitiveness of vegetable chip products produced by the selected crop producers?
 - 3.1 What strategic alternatives can be derived from the SWOT/TOWS analysis?
 - 3.2 Which strategies are most feasible and aligned with their resources and market conditions?
 - 3.3 How can these strategies be operationalized to improve sustainability and growth?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative descriptive research design to examine the strategic situation and marketability of selected vegetable chip producers in Planza, San Fernando, Camarines Sur, Philippines. A qualitative approach was deemed appropriate because the study sought to explore participants' perceptions of their competitive environment, operational constraints, and strategic positioning within a specific rural agricultural context (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The design enabled an in-depth, contextualized understanding of business realities without manipulating variables or imposing experimental controls.

The study was conducted in Planza, a rural community where small-scale farmers engage in high-value crop production and value-added processing activities, including vegetable chip manufacturing. Thirteen (13) active vegetable chip producers participated in the study. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure that only individuals directly involved in production and management were included, as they possessed firsthand knowledge relevant to the research objectives (Etikan et al., 2016; Saunders et al., 2019). All respondents had been operating for five to ten years. The majority were female producers managing small-scale farms ranging from less than one hectare to two hectares, reflecting the micro-enterprise nature of vegetable chip production in the locality.

Data were collected using a researcher-developed semi-structured interview guide aligned with the study objectives. The instrument consisted of fifteen (15) open-ended core questions with follow-up probes organized around product development and marketing strategies, branding and promotional activities, distribution channels, infrastructure and production capacity, and regulatory compliance and operational challenges. The semi-structured format ensured consistency across interviews while allowing flexibility for participants to elaborate on context-specific issues (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009). To establish content validity, the interview guide was reviewed by two experts in agribusiness and research methodology, and minor revisions were made to improve clarity and alignment with the study objectives. A pilot interview was conducted with one processor outside the study locale to refine question flow and enhance comprehensibility.

Data collection was conducted from September to October 2024. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the local producers' association prior to fieldwork. Participants were informed of the study's purpose and provided informed consent before the interviews. Face-to-face interviews were conducted at locations convenient to the participants and lasted approximately 30 to 60 minutes. Responses were documented through detailed field notes, which were reviewed and expanded immediately after each session to ensure completeness and accuracy.

The data were analyzed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework. The analysis involved repeated familiarization with the data, generation of initial codes, grouping of related codes into categories, review and refinement of emerging themes, definition and naming of final themes, and integration of themes into

the analytical narrative. This systematic process enabled the identification of recurring patterns related to marketability, competitiveness, infrastructure limitations, marketing capability gaps, regulatory challenges, and competitive pressures from established commercial brands.

To ensure methodological rigor, established criteria for trustworthiness were applied. Credibility was enhanced through prolonged engagement and clarificatory probing during interviews. Dependability was supported by systematic documentation of coding decisions and theme development. Confirmability was ensured by maintaining an audit trail of field notes and analytic memos. Transferability was addressed through detailed description of the study setting and participant characteristics.

This study focused exclusively on thirteen vegetable chip producers operating within Planza, San Fernando, Camarines Sur. The findings are context-specific and reflect the conditions of small-scale, farmer-led value-added enterprises in this rural setting. As the study relied on self-reported data, responses may be subject to recall bias or subjective interpretation. The qualitative design does not permit statistical generalization but provides analytical insights applicable to similar agribusiness contexts.

RESULTS

Market Position and Competitive Landscape of Vegetable Chip Producers

The findings indicate that vegetable chip producers in Planza, San Fernando, operate primarily as small-scale enterprises, with production conducted on a limited, intermittent basis. Production commonly depends on available agricultural surplus rather than structured market demand. For most respondents, vegetable chip processing serves as a supplementary livelihood activity rather than a fully commercialized business.

Sales transactions are mainly conducted through direct selling within local communities, at roadside stalls, and through repeat customer orders. Utilization of formal retail outlets, farmers' markets, and online selling platforms remains limited. Pricing practices are generally informal and influenced by prevailing competitor prices, buyer negotiation, and seasonal availability of raw materials.

Producers reported awareness of rising consumer demand for healthier snack alternatives, particularly preservative-free products. However, marketing activities remain largely dependent on personal selling networks with minimal promotional initiatives and branding practices.

Overall, the market operations of vegetable chip producers are characterized by localized distribution, small production scale, and reliance on informal marketing channels.

SWOT Analysis of Vegetable Chip Producers

Strengths. The results show that producers possess internal advantages, including preservative-free processing, locally sourced raw materials, product authenticity, and an existing base of repeat customers. Some producers have gained sales experience in nearby markets, providing familiarity with consumer demand.

Weaknesses. Identified weaknesses include the absence of strong brand identity, non-standardized packaging, limited promotional activities, minimal digital presence, and lack of structured marketing and management systems.

Opportunities. External opportunities identified include increasing consumer demand for healthier snack options, access to government assistance programs administered by the Department of Agriculture and the Department of Trade and Industry, participation in trade fairs, and potential entry into tourism-oriented markets such as pasalubong centers.

Threats. Major threats include competition from established commercial snack brands with wider distribution networks, stronger promotional strategies, and standardized product presentation. Competition from similar vegetable chip producers in other regions was also reported.

TOWS-Based Strategic Alternatives

Based on the SWOT findings, the TOWS analysis generated the following strategic alternatives:

- **SO Strategies:** Utilize preservative-free production and local sourcing to access health-conscious markets and trade opportunities.
- **WO Strategies:** Improve branding, packaging, and digital promotion through training programs and technology adoption.
- **ST Strategies:** Emphasize product authenticity and quality to compete with commercial snack brands.
- **WT Strategies:** Strengthen organizational practices, marketing systems, and operational management to reduce competitive vulnerability.

Challenges Faced by Vegetable Chip Producers

Financial Constraints. Producers rely primarily on personal savings and informal borrowing due to limited access to institutional financing. Irregular sales contribute to unstable cash flow and limited investment capacity. Financial management practices such as budgeting and cost monitoring are minimally applied.

Marketing Challenges. Marketing activities are concentrated within local communities, resulting in limited market reach. Weak branding, inconsistent packaging, and limited promotional efforts reduce product visibility and consumer recognition.

Infrastructure and Processing Limitations. Production activities are affected by inadequate water supply, unstable electricity availability, and dependence on basic processing equipment. These conditions influence production continuity and operational capacity.

Training and Development Gaps. Most producers depend on experience-based knowledge with limited exposure to formal training in food safety, marketing, and enterprise management.

Regulatory Compliance Constraints. Producers generally operate without formal registration or certification such as DTI, BIR, local permits, or FDA approval, limiting participation in formal retail markets.

Proposed Strategic Plan for Marketability Enhancement

The study formulated a strategic plan based on a SWOT/TOWS analysis and identified operational conditions.

Strategic Alternatives

Strategic options include product differentiation, branding improvement, regulatory compliance, distribution expansion, and capability enhancement.

Feasible Strategies

Resource-aligned strategies identified as feasible include:

- Development of unified branding and packaging,
- Adoption of low-cost digital marketing platforms,
- Gradual regulatory compliance,
- Expansion into nearby retail outlets,
- Implementation of marketing and financial management training.

Operationalization of Strategies

A phased five-year implementation framework was developed:

Year 1 – Market Foundation

- Branding improvement
- Business registration
- Digital marketing establishment
- Local distribution strengthening

Years 2–3 – Expansion Phase

- Regional market entry
- Product diversification

- Equipment upgrading
- Continuous training programs

Years 4–5 – Market Consolidation

- Brand strengthening
- Advanced marketing strategies
- Certification acquisition
- Exploration of broader markets

Performance indicators include sales growth, distribution expansion, brand recognition, and improvements in production efficiency.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that vegetable chip producers operate within small-scale and locally concentrated market systems characterized by informal marketing practices and limited production capacity. These enterprises largely depend on direct selling, community-based networks, and localized distribution channels. While such systems enable producers to maintain relatively low operating costs and maintain close relationships with local consumers, they also restrict market expansion and limit the ability to reach broader regional or institutional markets. Although producers recognize the growing consumer demand for healthier snack alternatives, existing operational and marketing structures appear insufficient to support wider market participation. As a result, the enterprises remain confined to localized market segments despite favorable market trends indicating increasing demand for vegetable-based snack products.

From the perspective of the Resource-Based View (RBV) (Barney, 1991), the producers possess several valuable internal resources that could potentially serve as sources of competitive advantage. These include access to locally produced agricultural raw materials, traditional processing knowledge, and the ability to produce preservative-free vegetable chips that align with current consumer preferences for healthier snack options. However, the findings suggest that these resources have not yet been strategically leveraged to achieve sustained competitive advantage. In RBV terms, while the resources may be valuable, they must also be rare, difficult to imitate, and effectively organized in order to generate long-term competitiveness (Barney, 1991). Without appropriate organizational capabilities—such as marketing management, brand development, and market intelligence—the potential value of these resources remains underutilized.

Similar observations have been reported in studies involving small agri-food enterprises where product quality alone does not ensure competitiveness without complementary managerial and marketing capabilities. According to Porter (2008), competitive advantage arises not only from possessing valuable resources but also from the ability to position products strategically within the market. Small enterprises often struggle to convert product advantages into market success because they lack formal marketing strategies, distribution systems, and brand positioning mechanisms. Research on small

and medium enterprises (SMEs) further suggests that managerial capability and marketing orientation significantly influence firm performance and market growth (Martin & Javalgi, 2016). In many developing economies, agro-processors rely primarily on product-based advantages while underinvesting in marketing capabilities that could improve market penetration.

The challenges related to branding, packaging, and promotion further illustrate the importance of marketing capabilities in determining product marketability. Weak branding strategies, limited packaging innovation, and minimal promotional activities constrain product visibility and consumer recognition. According to marketing principles articulated by Kotler and Keller (2016), product presentation, branding, and communication play a significant role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions, particularly in competitive food markets where consumers are often influenced by perceived quality and brand identity. Packaging, in particular, serves not only as a protective mechanism but also as a marketing tool that communicates product value and brand positioning (Rundh, 2016). Without distinctive packaging and consistent brand messaging, even high-quality products may struggle to compete against commercially established snack brands that invest heavily in product presentation and advertising.

These findings are also consistent with Porter's (2008) framework on competitive strategy. Small enterprises that lack economies of scale often face disadvantages when competing on price against larger manufacturers with greater production capacity and cost efficiencies. Consequently, differentiation strategies—such as emphasizing product quality, natural ingredients, local sourcing, and health benefits—become more viable competitive approaches for small-scale producers. Differentiation allows smaller firms to create perceived value among consumers, enabling them to compete beyond purely price-based considerations. However, effective differentiation requires the ability to communicate product attributes clearly through branding, packaging, and promotional strategies.

In addition to marketing constraints, the study identified several structural barriers that collectively limit enterprise growth and market expansion. Financial constraints restrict the ability of producers to invest in improved processing equipment, packaging materials, and marketing activities. Infrastructure limitations, including processing facilities and storage capacity, further affect production efficiency and product consistency. Studies on agribusiness development indicate that limited access to capital and inadequate infrastructure remain major barriers to the growth of small-scale agricultural enterprises in developing economies (Reardon et al., 2009). Without adequate financial and physical resources, producers are often unable to adopt technologies that improve productivity, product quality, and operational efficiency.

Training and capacity-building gaps also influence enterprise competitiveness. Limited exposure to business management training, marketing strategies, and product development techniques restricts the ability of producers to adapt to changing market conditions. According to Shepherd (2007), improving the marketing capabilities of smallholder-based agro-enterprises is essential for increasing their participation in value

chains and formal markets. Training programs that enhance entrepreneurial skills, marketing knowledge, and product innovation can significantly improve the performance of rural agribusiness enterprises.

Regulatory compliance also presents challenges for small-scale processors, particularly in meeting food safety standards and obtaining product certifications required for entry into formal retail markets. While regulatory frameworks are designed to ensure consumer protection and product quality, compliance requirements may impose additional costs and administrative burdens on small enterprises. Research on agri-food value chains suggests that small processors often struggle to meet certification and quality assurance requirements due to limited financial resources and technical knowledge (Trienekens, 2011). As a result, many enterprises continue to rely on informal markets where regulatory barriers are lower but growth opportunities are limited.

These interconnected challenges create a reinforcing cycle that constrains enterprise scalability. Limited financial resources reduce the ability to upgrade infrastructure or invest in marketing improvements, while inadequate marketing capacity limits sales growth that could otherwise generate the capital needed for expansion. Consequently, producers tend to rely on localized and informal selling systems such as direct community sales, small local retailers, or occasional market fairs. While these channels provide immediate income opportunities, they offer limited potential for long-term growth or broader market penetration.

The proposed strategic plan developed in this study responds directly to these conditions by aligning internal strengths with external market opportunities through a structured SWOT/TOWS framework. The strategies emphasize product differentiation, gradual formalization of business practices, expansion of distribution channels, and the development of marketing and managerial capabilities. By capitalizing on the natural and locally sourced attributes of the products, producers can position vegetable chips as healthier and more authentic snack alternatives. At the same time, incremental improvements in branding, packaging, and promotional strategies can enhance product visibility and consumer trust.

The phased implementation approach is particularly relevant in the context of small-scale rural enterprises where financial and organizational resources are limited. Rather than requiring immediate large-scale investments, the strategy prioritizes gradual capability development, allowing producers to strengthen their market position while operating within existing resource constraints. This approach reflects the principle that sustainable enterprise development often occurs through incremental improvements in organizational capabilities rather than rapid structural transformation.

Overall, the findings highlight the importance of integrating production capabilities with strategic marketing and organizational development in order to enhance the competitiveness of small-scale agribusiness enterprises. While vegetable chip producers possess valuable resources and operate within a market environment characterized by growing demand for healthier snack alternatives, the effective utilization of these

resources requires stronger marketing capabilities, improved infrastructure, and enhanced business management skills. Strategic alignment between internal resources and external market opportunities therefore emerges as a critical factor in achieving sustainable growth and improving the marketability of value-added agricultural products.

Conclusions

The study concludes that vegetable chip producers in Planza, San Fernando, operate within localized, small-scale market systems characterized by limited branding practices, informal marketing structures, and operational constraints.

Research Question 1:

Producers possess product-related strengths such as preservative-free processing and local sourcing; however, weaknesses in branding, management systems, and promotion limit competitive positioning despite favorable market opportunities.

Research Question 2:

Producers face interconnected challenges, including financial constraints, limited marketing capabilities, infrastructure deficiencies, training gaps, and regulatory compliance barriers, which affect production efficiency and market expansion.

Research Question 3:

A strategic plan based on SWOT/TOWS analysis identified differentiation, branding enhancement, regulatory formalization, distribution expansion, and capability development as feasible strategies. The phased implementation framework provides a practical pathway toward improving marketability and long-term competitiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Vegetable chip producers should establish a clear and standardized brand identity supported by improved packaging and product labeling to enhance market visibility.
2. Producers are encouraged to adopt digital marketing platforms and online selling channels to expand market reach beyond local communities.
3. Government agencies and local institutions may provide technical assistance to support business registration, food safety certification, and regulatory compliance.
4. Continuous capacity-building programs focusing on marketing, entrepreneurship, food safety, and financial management should be implemented for producers.
5. Formation of producer cooperatives or shared processing facilities may be encouraged to improve production efficiency and reduce operational costs.
6. Financial assistance programs and infrastructure support may be strengthened to enable small-scale producers to upgrade equipment and stabilize production operations.

7. Future studies may evaluate the implementation and long-term impact of the proposed strategic plan on enterprise growth and sustainability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the conduct of this study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection. Each participant was clearly informed of the study's purpose, the procedures involved, and the intended use of the information gathered. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and respondents were free to decline or withdraw at any time without negative consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were carefully maintained by assigning codes rather than using personal or business names in the presentation and analysis of the data. All information collected was handled in accordance with Data Privacy principles and was used solely for academic and research purposes. The well-being, rights, and dignity of the participants were safeguarded throughout the research process to ensure that no harm or disadvantage resulted from their participation.

The researchers declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Academic integrity was upheld by strictly avoiding plagiarism and properly acknowledging all sources of information used in the research. Objectivity was maintained in the analysis and interpretation of the findings to minimize researcher bias, and the results were presented solely on the basis of the collected data. Furthermore, artificial intelligence (AI)-assisted tools, including ChatGPT and Grammarly, were used solely for language editing, grammar refinement, and clarity in writing. These tools were not used for data generation, data analysis, or fabrication of research findings. Full responsibility for the accuracy, interpretation, and originality of the study remains with the researchers.

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